

DEVELOPMENT OF PHENOLIC RESIN NANOCOMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH NANODIAMOND

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the effects of nanodiamond (ND) on the structure and properties of phenolic resin nanocomposites were investigated. It was found that ND was well dispersed in the nanocomposites at low contents below 0.05 wt%. Regarding thermal properties, the nanocomposites containing 0.01 wt% ND exhibited the highest thermal decomposition temperature. In contrast, the rate of increase in thermal decomposition temperature was significantly reduced at higher filler contents above 0.5 wt%, suggesting the formation of severe agglomerates. Both the flexural modulus and flexural strength increased with the incorporation of ND at low contents, indicating that the strong reinforcement effects of ND were due to its high dispersibility and favorable interfacial interactions.

1 INTRODUCTION

So far, high-tensile steel and aluminum alloy materials have often been used for transportation equipment. In recent years, global environmental concerns have driven efforts to reduce the weight of car and aircraft to improve fuel efficiency. Therefore, polymer composites, which have a lower specific gravity than metallic materials, have attracted a great deal of attention as alternative materials.

Phenolic resin (PF) is well known for their excellent electrical insulation, heat resistance and flame resistance. They have been used in industrial applications such as insulators for automotive parts and circuit boards. Due to its rigidity, it is difficult to incorporate other materials to PF by conventional methods such as solvent mixing or melt mixing. To the best of our knowledge, there are very few reports on PF composites with improved mechanical or thermal properties.

In this study, we prepared PF nanocomposites with nanocarbons by *in-situ* polymerization. We used nanodiamond (ND) as filler. ND is a nanocarbon with a particle size of less than 10 nm with primary diamond particles in the core. It shows high strength, high elastic modulus and high thermal conductivity derived from diamond. In addition, ND can disperse at nano-scale in water due to abundant oxygen-containing functional groups, such as hydroxy groups, carboxy groups and carbonyl groups, on the surface. Prior to the polymerization, ND was dispersed in the solvent and then PF was polymerized under the presence of ND. The structure and the properties of the PF/ND nanocomposites were evaluated.

2 SAMPLE PREPARATION

PF was mixed with ND/ethanol dispersion and sodium hydroxide. The mixture was stirred and heated in an oil bath for 20 minutes. When the temperature reached 80 °C formaldehyde solution was added to the mixture. After the reaction, the mixture was cooled to room temperature and then cased on aluminum cups, vacuum dried followed by curing. PF/ND nanocomposites with the filler content of 0 ~ 0.5 wt% with a thickness of about 1 mm were prepared.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 SEM

Figure 1 SEM images of PF and PF/ND nanocomposites.

Figure 1 shows SEM images of PF and PF/ND nanocomposites. It was found that ND were well dispersed in the nanocomposites at filler contents of 0.01 wt% and 0.05 wt%. On the other hand, agglomerates of ND were observed in the nanocomposites with 0.1 wt% or higher. The size of the agglomerates increased as the filler content increased, suggesting that agglomeration was promoted as the inter-particle distance decreased.

3.2 Thermal Properties

Figure 2 shows thermogravimetric traces of PF and PF/ND nanocomposites. The 5% weight loss on this curve is defined as the thermal decomposition temperature. The thermal decomposition temperature increased by the addition of ND.

Figure 3 shows thermal decomposition temperature of PF and PF/ND nanocomposites. The nanocomposites with a filler content of 0.1 wt% showed the highest thermal decomposition temperature, and it was 44 °C higher than that of PF. It was suggested that the movement of PF molecular chains were effectively suppressed by the highly dispersed ND with high interfacial area, resulted in significant improvement of resistance. On the other hand, the thermal decomposition temperature decreased for the nanocomposites with a filler content of more than 0.5 wt%. As shown before, ND formed serious agglomerates at high filler content. Therefore, the reinforcement effect decreased due to the decreased interfacial area. In addition, these agglomerates could cause heat concentration, that brought the thermal decomposition of the material.

Figure 2 Thermogravimetric traces of PF and PF/ND nanocomposites.

Figure 3 Thermal decomposition temperature of PF and PF/ND nanocomposites.

3.2 Mechanical Properties

Figure 4 Stress-strain curves of PF and PF/ND nanocomposites.

Figure 5 Flexural modulus and flexural strength of PF and PF/ND nanocomposites.

Figure 4 shows stress-strain curves of PF and PF/ND nanocomposites. The maximum stress corresponds to the flexural strength, and the initial gradient corresponds to the flexural modulus.

Figure 5 (A) shows flexural modulus and Figure 5 (B) shows flexural strength of PF and PF/ND nanocomposites. The flexural modulus increased with the increasing of ND content. Compared to PF, the flexural modulus increased by 38% at a filler content of 0.1 wt% and increased by 50% at a filler content of 0.5 wt%. Similarly, the flexural strength increased with increasing of ND content up to 0.1 wt%. Compared to PF, the flexural strength increased by 36% at a filler content of 0.1 %. However, the increasing rate started to decrease at the filler content of 0.5 wt%. In the low filler content region, ND were highly dispersed in PF, resulting in an excellent reinforcing effect. On the other hand, above a filler content of 0.5 wt%, the nanocomposites showed brittle behavior due to stress concentration caused by aggregates.

3.3 Interfacial interactions

Figure 6 Scheme of interfacial interactions in PF/ND nanocomposites.

Figure 6 shows scheme of interfacial interactions in PF/ND nanocomposites. The thermal and mechanical properties shown above are thought to be largely influenced by the dispersibility of ND in PF and the interaction at the interface between PF and ND. As mentioned before, ND has abundant oxygen-containing functional groups on their surface. Therefore, ND can form hydrogen bonds with phenolic groups of PF. In addition, it was assumed that π - π interactions were formed at the interface between the graphite of ND and the benzene ring of PF. These strong interfacial interactions together with the high dispersibility can be the main factor for the enhancement in the mechanical properties as well as the thermal properties.

4 CONCLUSIONS

PF/ND nanocomposites were prepared by *in-situ* polymerization. In the PF nanocomposites ND were well dispersed in the nanocomposites up to 0.1 wt% or lower. The thermal decomposition temperature increased by the incorporation of ND. The flexural modulus and the flexural strength increased by the incorporation of ND.